

EELISA

European University

EELISA MEDIA CHANNELS FOR INNOVATION

Deliverable 7.5

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

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Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP7 – “Create the ‘embedding’ for EELISA-wide R & I structures (Optimize outreach)”, as deliverable D7.5 “EELISA media channels for innovation” of the project EELISA INNOVation and COmmon REsearch strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), co-funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101035811.

The document details the EELISA media channels to be used to maximize the impact of R & I actions. These media channels are specific to the target audiences of the different tasks in WP7, but they can also contribute to maximize the impact of R & I actions of EELISA as a whole and will be shared with the EELISA Communication Office. Within the framework of WP7, we can distinguish between two different target audiences for which we need specific media channels: First, we target the general public at our universities and beyond with the EELISA Innovation Talks (task 7.4). Second, we target employees of innovation hubs, business incubators, and knowledge and technology transfer services, students, start-ups, founders, and maybe even investors with the innovation and entrepreneurship activities in EELISA InnoCORE (task 7.1 “Interaction platforms and citizen science”, task 7.2 “Create an infrastructure of business incubators across EELISA”, and task 7.3 “Implementing an EELISA-wide start-up initiative”). The EELISA media channels for innovation are basically differentiated according to these two different target audiences.

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Responsibles for EELISA media channels for innovation under EELISA InnoCORE

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for EELISA media channels for innovation
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Claudio Feijoo (claudio.feijoo@upm.es) Isabel Salgueiro (isabel.salgueiro@upm.es) Elena Berga (elena.bmontardit@upm.es)
École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	ENPC	Charlotte Huber (charlotte.huber@enpc.fr) Laura Molinari (laura.molinari@enpc.fr)
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	David Schkade (david.schkade@fau.de) Julia Rosenbusch (julia.rosenbusch@fau.de)
İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	İTÜ	Mehmet Ercek (ercekme@itu.edu.tr)
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Chiara Cappelli (chiara.cappelli@sns.it) Claudia Giua (claudia.giua@sns.it)
Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	SSSA	Monia Gentile (monia1.gentile@santannapisa.it) Elisa Guidi (elisa.guidi@santannapisa.it) Fatimata Pietra (Fatimata.Pietra@santannapisa.it)
Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	UPB	Ciprian Dobre (ciprian.dobre@upb.ro) Radu Ciobanu (radu.ciobanu@upb.ro)
Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	BME	Attila Joó (jo.attila@emk.bme.hu) Zsolt Gémesi (gemesi.zsolt@bme.hu)
Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Antoine Mercier (antoine.mercier@chimieparistech.psl.eu)

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Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Innovation Talks. EELISA Innovation Talks aim to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness – for the knowledge generated in EELISA and are publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematise the use of technology for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

R & I. Research and Innovation

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 41 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 General Considerations

In order to maximize the impact of the R & I actions undertaken in EELISA InnoCORE WP7 (“Create the ‘embedding’ for EELISA-wide R & I structures (Optimize outreach)”), we will use central EELISA media channels on the one hand and additionally local media channels of EELISA partners on the other hand. However, this is not the only important distinction with regard to EELISA media channels for innovation. The reason for this is that the different tasks in WP7 are aimed at different target groups: First, with the EELISA Innovation Talks (task 7.4) we target the general public at our universities and beyond. Second, with the innovation and entrepreneurship activities in EELISA InnoCORE (task 7.1 “Interaction platforms and citizen science”, task 7.2 “Create an infrastructure of business incubators across EELISA”, and task 7.3 “Implementing an EELISA-wide start-up initiative”) we target employees of innovation hubs, business incubators, and knowledge and technology transfer services, students, start-ups, founders, and maybe even investors. As a consequence of this relatively sharp distinction between these two target groups, we will use different central EELISA media channels as well as different local media channels of EELISA partners for streaming and promoting EELISA Innovation Talks on the one hand and for promoting innovation and entrepreneurship activities in EELISA InnoCORE on the other hand.

These different EELISA media channels for innovation are not just indispensable for maximizing the impact of R & I actions undertaken in EELISA InnoCORE WP7, but can also be helpful for maximizing the impact of R & I actions of EELISA as a whole. Consequently, the EELISA media channels for innovation will be shared with the EELISA communication and dissemination structures, i.e., the EELISA Communication Office, EELISA InnoCORE WP1 for the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities — the input of D7.5 will be taken into account and will feed in the update of D1.1 ‘Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan’ —, EELISA WP9 and EELISA Unfolds. This will help to improve future EELISA communication activities.

2.1 EELISA media channels for EELISA Innovation Talks

EELISA Innovation Talks aim to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness – for the knowledge generated in EELISA and are publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematize the use of technology for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. We aim at establishing two main (regular) formats that both are held publicly, rotating between the cities of our partnership, and streamed via media channels: a publicly visible panel discussion format, where EELISA scientists discuss current sociotechnological developments with leaders from science, industry and politics, but also with students and participants of civil society. And a second line of interactive formats like fishbowl discussions, science slams or bar camps aiming at a younger audience and established with a strong involvement of young scientists. EELISA Communities – and in particular the results from challenges – will be the main source to feed this activity. We particularly aim at reflecting European topics, referring to the latest European legislation and policy frameworks and regularly inviting experts from European politics. Furthermore, in order to achieve the main goal of EELISA Innovation Talks which is to raise public and thus also scientific awareness for the knowledge generated in EELISA, we will try out other formats that may contribute to achieving this goal and making EELISA Innovation Talks a success and a shop window for EELISA as a whole.

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For achieving this ambitious goal of reaching out to the broader public we need EELISA media channels for streaming and promoting EELISA Innovation Talks. These media channels will be located on two different levels to increase their impact: On the first level, we will use the central EELISA media channels for EELISA Innovation Talks, and on the second level, we will also use the local media channels of EELISA partners to promote EELISA Innovation Talks.

2.1.1 The central EELISA media channels for EELISA Innovation Talks

On the level of the central EELISA media channels for EELISA Innovation Talks we will make use of a whole variety of media channels: First, we will use the EELISA website (<https://eelisa.eu>) where we will create a subpage for EELISA Innovation Talks. Moreover, we will also use the existing News & Events subpage of the EELISA website (<https://eelisa.eu/news-events/>) for announcing EELISA Innovation Talks in the events section and for promoting EELISA Innovation Talks in the news section. The contact person for these websites is the EELISA Communication Officer, Yolanda Pividal (yolanda.pividal@eelisa.eu). Second, in addition to the EELISA website, EELISA Innovation Talks will also be announced in the EELISA newsletter. The contact for the EELISA newsletter is the EELISA communication team (uptodate@eelisa.eu). Third, we will also use the existing EELISA social media channels. The EELISA YouTube channel will be used for streaming EELISA Innovation Talks and the EELISA Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook accounts will be used for promoting EELISA Innovation Talks. The contact person for these social media channels is the EELISA Social Media Manager, Lucía Gavilán (lucia.gavilan@eelisa.eu). All EELISA Innovation Talks will be permanently available on the EELISA YouTube channel as well as on the EELISA website where a subpage for EELISA Innovation Talks will be created. So even after the events took place, they will still be available and serve as a permanent shop window for the knowledge generated in EELISA.

2.1.2 The local media channels of EELISA partners to promote EELISA Innovation Talks

The first level of the central EELISA media channels for EELISA Innovation Talks targets more or less all those who are already involved in EELISA. Relying solely on this first level, however, would severely limit the target audience of EELISA Innovation Talks. To overcome the limitations of the first level, we will additionally make use of a second level: The local media channels of EELISA partners to promote EELISA Innovation Talks. In such a way, we will reach out to the general public at our universities and beyond to all those not yet involved in EELISA as well. Here again, we will make use of a whole variety of media channels:

First, we will contact the EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives to inform them about each particular EELISA Innovation Talk. Currently, these representatives are the following:

Partner	Acronym	EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Claudio Feijoo (claudio.feijoo@upm.es) Isabel Salgueiro (isabel.salgueiro@upm.es) Elena Berga (elena.bmontardit@upm.es)
École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	ENPC	Charlotte Huber (charlotte.huber@enpc.fr) Laura Molinari (laura.molinari@enpc.fr)

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İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	İTÜ	Mehmet Ercek (ercekme@itu.edu.tr)
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Chiara Cappelli (chiara.cappelli@sns.it) Claudia Giua (claudia.giua@sns.it)
Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	SSSA	Monia Gentile (monia1.gentile@santannapisa.it) Elisa Guidi (elisa.guidi@santannapisa.it) Fatimata Pietra (Fatimata.Pietra@santannapisa.it)
Universitatea Politehnica din București	UPB	Ciprian Dobre (ciprian.dobre@upb.ro) Radu Ciobanu (radu.ciobanu@upb.ro)
Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	BME	Attila Joó (joo.attila@emk.bme.hu) Zsolt Gémesi (gemesi.zsolt@bme.hu)
Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Antoine Mercier (antoine.mercier@chimieparistech.psl.eu)

Table 2: List of EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives

Second, we will use the websites of our universities in order to announce EELISA Innovation Talks. Here is an overview of those websites and contacts for those websites:

Partner	Websites	Contacts
UPM	www.upm.es www.actuaupm.blogspot.com https://eventos.upm.es/ https://www.upm.es/UPM/SalaPrensa/epolitecnica_inv?prefmt=articulo&fmt=detail&id=ca5571bcc7c98410VgnVCM10000009c7648a	comunicacion@upm.es beatriz.delrincon@upm.es isabel.salgueiro@upm.es
ENPC	https://www.ecoledesponts.fr/en	site-internet@enpc.fr
FAU	www.fau.de www.fau.eu	webredaktion@fau.de
İTÜ	https://www.itu.edu.tr/en https://global.itu.edu.tr	aysekoc@itu.edu.tr
SNS	www.sns.it/eelisa www.sns.it/en/eelisa www.sns.it/it www.sns.it/en	eelisa@sns.it sitosns@sns.it
SSSA	www.santannapisa.it	ufficio.stampa@santannapisa.it

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UPB	https://upb.ro/eelisa/ https://upb.ro/	alin.matei@upb.ro
BME	www.fiek.bme.hu https://www.bme.hu/	flachner.bernadett@bme.hu (for fiiek) szemere.dorottya@bme.hu (for fiiek) molnar.balint@bme.hu (for bme)
PSL	https://psl.eu/en/innovation-entrepreneurship https://psl.eu/actualites	nelly.manoukian@psl.eu (for innovation-entrepreneurship) emilie.bremond@psl.eu (for actualites)

Table 3: List of EELISA partners' websites and contacts for announcing EELISA Innovation Talks

Third, all of our institutions have newsletters in which we will announce EELISA Innovation Talks. Here is an overview of the contacts responsible for the newsletters in which EELISA Innovation Talks will be announced at each institution:

Partner	Newsletter	Contacts
UPM	Newsletter UPM R&D Updates (Newsletter of the UPM Vice Rectorate for Research, Innovation & Doctoral Studies)	ana.galan@upm.es
ENPC	ENPC monthly newsletter	laura.molinari@enpc.fr
FAU	FAU newsletter (usually 14-day newsletter to all FAU members)	newsletter@fau.de
ITÜ	ITU newsletter	aysekoc@itu.edu.tr
SNS	SNS newsletter	tiziana.paladini@sns.it eelisa@sns.it
SSSA	JoTTO newsletter	uvr@santannapisa.it
UPB	International Relations Newsletter (published every two months)	alin.matei@upb.ro
BME	FIEK newsletter BME newsletter	flachner.bernadett@bme.hu (for FIEK) szemere.dorottya@bme.hu (for FIEK) molnar.balint@bme.hu (for BME)
PSL	PSL newsletter	nelly.manoukian@psl.eu

Table 4: List of EELISA partners' newsletters and contacts for announcing EELISA Innovation Talks

Fourth, we will use the social media channels of our institutions to promote EELISA Innovation Talks. Here is an overview of those social media channels and the contacts who manage them:

Partner	Social media channels	Contacts
UPM	https://www.instagram.com/actuaupm/ https://www.instagram.com/somosupm/	comunicacion@upm.es (for UPM general)

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	https://twitter.com/La_UPM https://twitter.com/actuaupm https://twitter.com/otri_upm https://twitter.com/opi_upm https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidad-politecnica-de-madrid/ https://www.linkedin.com/in/actuaupm/ https://www.linkedin.com/company/opi-upm/ https://es-es.facebook.com/universidadpolitecnica-demadrid/ https://es-es.facebook.com/actuaupm/ https://www.facebook.com/opi.upm/	beatriz.delrincon@upm.es (for @actuaupm) otri.investigacion@upm.es (for @otri_upm) ana.galan@upm.es (for @opi_upm)
ENPC	https://www.instagram.com/ecoledesponts/ https://twitter.com/EcoledesPonts https://fr.linkedin.com/school/ecole-des-ponts-paris-tech/ https://www.facebook.com/EcoledesPonts/	karin.danjaume@enpc.fr
FAU	www.instagram.com/uni_fau www.twitter.com/unifau https://de.linkedin.com/school/fau-erlangen-nürnberg/ www.facebook.com/Uni.Erlangen.Nuernberg www.facebook.com/fauenglish	socialmedia@fau.de
ITÜ	https://www.instagram.com/itu1773 https://twitter.com/itu1773en https://www.linkedin.com/school/itu1773/ https://www.facebook.com/itu1773/	aysekoc@itu.edu.tr
SNS	https://www.instagram.com/scuolanormale https://twitter.com/scuolanormale https://it.linkedin.com/school/scuola-normale-superiore/ https://it-it.facebook.com/scuolanormale/	social@sns.it
SSSA	https://www.instagram.com/studiarealsantanna https://twitter.com/ScuolaSantanna	ufficio.stampa@santannapisa.it

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	https://www.linkedin.com/school/scuola-superiore-sant'anna/	
	https://www.facebook.com/scuolasuperioresantanna/ https://www.instagram.com/upb1818	
UPB	https://twitter.com/upb1818 https://ro.linkedin.com/school/upb1818/ https://www.facebook.com/UPB1818 https://www.tiktok.com/@upb1818	alin.matei@upb.ro
BME	https://www.instagram.com/z10bme/ https://www.instagram.com/budapestuniversity https://twitter.com/BME_hu https://www.linkedin.com/company/bme-fiek/ https://www.linkedin.com/school/budapest-university-of-technology-and-economics/ https://www.facebook.com/BMEFIEK https://www.facebook.com/Muegyetem.hu/	flachner.bernadett@bme.hu (for Z10 and FIEK) szemere.dorottya@bme.hu (for Z10 and FIEK) molnar.balint@bme.hu (for BME)
PSL	https://www.instagram.com/psl_univ https://twitter.com/psl_univ https://www.linkedin.com/school/universit-psl/ https://www.facebook.com/PSLuniv/	nelly.manoukian@psl.eu

Table 5: List of EELISA partners’ social media channels for promoting EELISA Innovation Talks

2.2 EELISA media channels for innovation and entrepreneurship activities

In EELISA InnoCORE we will offer and promote a whole variety of innovation and entrepreneurship activities: In Task 7.1, we will offer EELISA-wide consulting, trainings and joint events on innovation processes, exchange best practices for social prototyping and run test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include evaluation of user experiences. Furthermore, we may also use our innovation hubs for running and streaming public events and talks. In Task 7.2, we will work out the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan that will be rolled out in the third year of funding: This will include joint information campaigns and parallel events (e.g. start-up-contests, hackathons or mentoring programmes) across our partner cities. Closely connected to this are the entrepreneurship activities in Task 7.3, namely joint activities to raise the probability of a successful market entry of start-ups in all our partner cities and eventually across the entire EELISA innovation ecosystem. Those activities will include workshops and boot camps to inform participants on how investors actually work in different national markets and to convey general basics like “product market fit”, “investor readiness”, “pitching” or “negotiation”. Moreover, we will foster networking of existing founders

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and start-ups with each other and on-site by local events in order to offer them access to the respective ecosystem. As a further measure, we will organize a start-up contest, potentially in the form of a roadshow, i.e. pitching events for start-ups in every location of the EELISA network with a grand “finale” in Erlangen-Nuremberg, to which the winners of the local competitions are invited.

For the implementation of these ambitious innovation and entrepreneurship activities, we need to reach out to our innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems where we have to promote these activities and for this in turn EELISA media channels are indispensable. These media channels will again be located on two different levels to increase their impact: On the first level, we will use the central EELISA media channels to promote our innovation and entrepreneurship activities, and on the second level, we will use the local media channels of EELISA partners to promote the same activities.

2.2.1 The central EELISA media channels for innovation and entrepreneurship activities

On the level of the central EELISA media channels for innovation and entrepreneurship activities, we will use a whole range of media channels (which are identical to those of EELISA Innovation Talks, with the exception of the dedicated subpage for EELISA Innovation Talks): First, we will use the existing News & Events subpage of the EELISA website (<https://eelisa.eu/news-events/>) for announcing our innovation and entrepreneurship activities in the events section and for promoting these activities in the news section. The contact person for these websites is the EELISA Communication Officer, Yolanda Pividal (yolanda.pividal@eelisa.eu). Second, in addition to the EELISA website, our innovation and entrepreneurship activities will also be announced in the EELISA newsletter. The contact for the EELISA newsletter is the EELISA communication team (uptodate@eelisa.eu). Third, we will also use the existing EELISA social media channels. The EELISA YouTube channel will be used for streaming innovation and entrepreneurship activities and the EELISA Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook accounts will be used for promoting our innovation and entrepreneurship activities. The contact person for these social media channels is the EELISA Social Media Manager, Lucía Gavilán (lucia.gavilan@eelisa.eu).

2.2.2 The local media channels of EELISA partners for innovation and entrepreneurship activities

Probably even more important in reaching out to our innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems than the central EELISA media channels for innovation and entrepreneurship activities are the local media channels of EELISA partners for innovation and entrepreneurship activities. While on the first level of the central EELISA media channels we address more or less all those who are already involved in EELISA, on the second level of the local media channels of EELISA partners, we go one step further and also reach out to all those in our local innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems who are not yet involved in EELISA. This will allow us to increase our outreach significantly. And also here we will make use of a whole variety of media channels:

First, we will contact the EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives to inform them about each particular of our innovation and entrepreneurship activities. Currently, these representatives are the following:

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Partner	Acronym	EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Claudio Feijoo (claudio.feijoo@upm.es) Isabel Salgueiro (isabel.salgueiro@upm.es) Elena Berga (elena.bmontardit@upm.es)
École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	ENPC	Charlotte Huber (charlotte.huber@enpc.fr) Laura Molinari (laura.molinari@enpc.fr)
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	David Schkade (david.schkade@fau.de) Julia Rosenbusch (julia.rosenbusch@fau.de)
İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	İTÜ	Mehmet Ercek (ercekme@itu.edu.tr)
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Chiara Cappelli (chiara.cappelli@sns.it) Claudia Giua (claudia.giua@sns.it)
Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	SSSA	Monia Gentile (monia1.gentile@santannapisa.it) Elisa Guidi (elisa.guidi@santannapisa.it) Fatimata Pietra (Fatimata.Pietra@santannapisa.it)
Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	UPB	Ciprian Dobre (ciprian.dobre@upb.ro) Radu Ciobanu (radu.ciobanu@upb.ro)
Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	BME	Attila Joó (joo.attila@emk.bme.hu) Zsolt Gémesi (gemesi.zsolt@bme.hu)
Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Antoine Mercier (antoine.mercier@chimieparistech.psl.eu)

Table 6: List of EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives

Second, we will use the websites of our universities' innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem in order to announce our innovation and entrepreneurship activities. Here is an overview of those websites and contacts for those websites:

Partner	Websites	Contacts
UPM	www.actuaupm.blogspot.com https://eventos.upm.es/	beatriz.delrincon@upm.es
ENPC	https://www.ecoledesponts.fr/en	site-internet@enpc.fr
FAU	https://www.fau.de/outreach/innovationen-und-gruendungen/gruenden/	christoph.heyne@fau.de kerstin.reuss@fau.de
İTÜ	https://ariteknokent.com.tr/en https://innogate.org/en/homepage/ https://itucekirdek.com/ https://itumagnet.com/en/homepage/ http://www.ginova.itu.edu.tr/	melike.kus@ariteknokent.com.tr basak.tetikoz@ariteknokent.com.tr alpyurttas@itu.edu.tr

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SNS	www.sns.it/eelisa	eelisa@sns.it sitosns@sns.it
	www.sns.it/en/eelisa	
	www.sns.it/it	
	www.sns.it/en	
SSSA	www.santannapisa.it	ufficio.stampa@santannapisa.it
UPB	http://antreprenoriat.upb.ro/en/	alin.matei@upb.ro
	https://upb.ro/acceleratoare-tehnologie/	
	https://upb.ro/stiriupb/	
BME	www.fiek.bme.hu	flachner.bernadett@bme.hu szemere.dorottya@bme.hu
	https://psl.eu/en/innovation-entrepreneurship	nelly.manoukian@psl.eu

Table 7: List of EELISA partners' websites and contacts for announcing EELISA innovation and entrepreneurship activities

Third, all of our institutions have newsletters in which we will announce our innovation and entrepreneurship activities. Here is an overview of the contacts responsible for the newsletters in which our innovation and entrepreneurship activities will be announced at each institution:

Partner	Newsletter	Contacts
UPM	Newsletter UPM R&D Updates (Newsletter of the UPM Vice Rectorate for Research, Innovation & Doctoral Studies)	ana.galan@upm.es
ENPC	ENPC monthly newsletter	laura.molinari@enpc.fr
FAU	Existency newsletter	kerstin.reuss@fau.de (for Existency newsletter)
	newsletter of the consulting services for start-up businesses	christoph.heyne@fau.de
ITÜ	ARI teknokent newsletter	melike.kus@ariteknokent.com.tr basak.tetikoz@ariteknokent.com.tr
	ITU EELISA newsletter	aysekoc@itu.edu.tr (for ITU EELISA newsletter)
	ITU GINOVA newsletter	alpyurttas@itu.edu.tr (for ITU GINOVA newsletter)
SNS	JoTTO newsletter	eelisa@sns.it
SSSA	JoTTO newsletter	uvr@santannapisa.it
UPB	International Relations Newsletter (published every two months)	alin.matei@upb.ro
BME	FIEK newsletter	flachner.bernadett@bme.hu szemere.dorottya@bme.hu

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PSL	PSL newsletter	nelly.manoukian@psl.eu
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Table 8: List of EELISA partners' newsletters and contacts for announcing EELISA innovation and entrepreneurship activities

Fourth, we will use the social media channels of our institutions to promote EELISA innovation and entrepreneurship activities. Here is an overview of those social media channels and the contacts who manage them:

Partner	Social media channels	Contacts
UPM	https://www.instagram.com/actuaupm/ https://www.instagram.com/somosupm/ https://twitter.com/La_UPM https://twitter.com/actuaupm https://twitter.com/otri_upm https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidad-politecnica-de-madrid/ https://www.linkedin.com/in/actuaupm/ https://es-es.facebook.com/universidadpolitecnicaademadrid/ https://es-es.facebook.com/actuaupm/	comunicacion@upm.es (for UPM general) beatriz.delrincon@upm.es (for @actuaupm) otri.investigacion@upm.es (for @otri_upm)
ENPC	https://www.instagram.com/ecoledesponts/ https://twitter.com/EcoledesPonts https://fr.linkedin.com/school/ecole-des-ponts-paris-tech/ https://www.facebook.com/EcoledesPonts/	karin.danjaume@enpc.fr
FAU	https://www.instagram.com/existencyofficial/ https://www.instagram.com/dtafau https://twitter.com/faudta https://de.linkedin.com/company/gründerbüro-der-friedrich-alexander-universität-erlangen-nürnberg https://www.linkedin.com/company/existency/ https://de.linkedin.com/company/faudta https://www.facebook.com/existencyofficial https://www.facebook.com/faudta/	lisa.wittenzellner@fau.de
ITÜ	https://www.instagram.com/ituariteknoent/ https://www.instagram.com/innogateorg/	melike.kus@ariteknoent.com.tr

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	https://www.instagram.com/itucekirdek/ https://www.instagram.com/itumagnet/ https://www.instagram.com/ituginova/ https://twitter.com/aritekknokent https://twitter.com/innogateorg https://twitter.com/itucekirdek https://twitter.com/itumagnet https://twitter.com/ITUginova https://www.linkedin.com/company/ituaritekknokent/ https://www.linkedin.com/company/innogate/mycompany/ https://www.linkedin.com/company/itucekirdek https://www.linkedin.com/company/itumagnet/ https://de.linkedin.com/company/itu-ginova https://www.facebook.com/aritekknokent https://www.facebook.com/innogateorg https://www.facebook.com/itucekirdek/ https://www.facebook.com/itumagnet/ https://www.facebook.com/ITUginova	basak.tetikoz@aritekknokent.com.tr aysekoc@itu.edu.tr alpyurtas@itu.edu.tr
SNS	https://www.instagram.com/scuolanormale https://twitter.com/scuolanormale https://it.linkedin.com/school/scuola-normale-superiore/ https://it-it.facebook.com/scuolanormale/	social@sns.it
SSSA	https://www.instagram.com/studiarealsantanna https://twitter.com/ScuolaSantanna https://www.linkedin.com/school/scuola-superiore-sant'anna/ https://www.facebook.com/scuolasuperioresantanna/ https://twitter.com/jointto_it https://www.linkedin.com/in/jotto-joint-technology-transfer-office/recent-activity/posts/ https://www.facebook.com/Jointto.it/	ufficio.stampa@santannapisa.it

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UPB	https://www.instagram.com/upb1818 https://twitter.com/upb1818 https://ro.linkedin.com/school/upb1818/ https://www.facebook.com/UPB1818	alin.matei@upb.ro
BME	https://www.instagram.com/z10bme/ https://www.linkedin.com/company/bme-fiek/ https://www.facebook.com/BMEFIEK	flachner.bernadett@bme.hu szemere.dorottya@bme.hu
PSL	https://www.instagram.com/psl_univ https://twitter.com/psl_univ https://www.linkedin.com/school/universit-psl/ https://www.facebook.com/PSLuniv/	nelly.manoukian@psl.eu

Table 9: List of EELISA partners' social media channels for promoting EELISA innovation and entrepreneurship activities

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